

Mistra C2B2 annual report 2023–2024:

Towards a sustainable governance of the Swedish blue economy

Annual report 2023–2024

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About C2B2

C2B2 is a research programme hosted by the University of Gothenburg and funded by the Swedish Foundation for Strategic Environmental Research (Mistra). The scope of the programme is to find a sustainable way to govern the Swedish water basins. C2B2 started in September 2023 and will run for four years, with a possible extension of four more years. Eleven research organisations are partners in C2B2. Get in touch: www.c2b2.se, c2b2@gu.se

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A year of 16 months

Since its launch in September 2023, the research programme Mistra C2B2 has grown from zero to fully operational and is now moving into new phases. It is an exciting development, according to programme director Torsten Linders.

– It has largely worked as we had planned, he says.

Leading a research programme is a complex task, and Torsten Linders describes it as a job that requires managing many different threads simultaneously.

– It involves a large group of people from multiple organizations. It has been very satisfying to see how the collaboration has taken off and entered various productive stages. The funding from Mistra allows us to think big and long-term, he says.

By the official launch of C2B2 in the fall of 2023, much was already in place. Researchers were affiliated with the programme, and stakeholders had been engaged.

– Since then, some adjustments have been made. New participants have joined, while others have stepped away.

What have been the most significant milestones during these first 16 months?

– I would say the launch of two of the three LivingLabs, covering the Baltic Sea proper as well as the Kattegat and Skagerrak. That is not the only important development within the programme, but the labs are central. The idea is that the other work packages will contribute with knowledge, data, and solutions to our teams, while also generating insights on which issues are most relevant to address.

Has the work within the LivingLabs progressed well?

– Overall, it has gone as we had hoped. We have presented the structure to stakeholders and secured their agreement that it is a sound approach.

Are these the stakeholders you had in mind?

– Yes, we have involved the fishing industry, the offshore wind power sector, maritime transport, and various authorities.

During most of the period covered by this first annual report, we were also fortunate to have the Swedish Armed Forces engaged, even at the highest level, with former Chief of the Navy Ewa Skoog Haslum on our board. We were very proud to have her involved and hope that someone else from the navy will take her place on the board moving forward.

Have the armed forces also participated in the LivingLabs?

– That remains an ambition we have not yet achieved. In general, we would like to see greater involvement from authorities, but finding the right framework for their participation in a LivingLab setting is a challenge.

What challenges are you referring to?

– Sometimes, there is an expectation that authorities will simply take note of what other stakeholders propose. ‘We have reached this conclusion, now you need to regulate accordingly’.

Is interest among stakeholders still strong?

– Yes, and new ones are joining all the time.

How have they reacted to collaborating within the LivingLabs?

– The concept is working as intended. However, given that multiple interests and perspectives are involved, some friction is inevitable. Everyone understood this from the outset. The conflicts of interest already existed. Bringing stakeholders together in the same room gives us a chance to work constructively and find solutions together. That is a key part of our mission.

What kind of feedback have you received from participants?

– I would say that both researchers and stakeholders are cautiously optimistic. There is ongoing work to evaluate and refine the method, especially as external conditions change. We must be prepared to adapt when the seascape shifts.

Can you give an example?

– When we started C2B2, the security situation in the Baltic Sea was already tense. We anticipated that it could deteriorate further, and that is exactly what has happened. From that perspective, the government’s decision last autumn regarding offshore wind power in the Baltic Sea was not entirely unexpected. However, it was clearly a setback for stakeholders developing offshore wind power in the region.

Have you encountered any broader challenges within the programme?

– None that were unexpected. Our ambitions are high, and we must balance a wide range of interests.

Why is the work within C2B2 important?

– We are working under Mistra’s mandate to develop knowledge-based governance for the blue economy. At the same time, we recognize that competition for space at sea is increasing. If we are to create governance structures that work, we must do so in collaboration with those who operate in these waters. Many different actors want to use the ocean, and it is becoming increasingly crowded.

On a more personal level, what do you gain from this work?

– Being part of a collective effort and seeing how various research disciplines can collaborate and contribute is incredibly rewarding. I get to witness firsthand how marine science integrates into a broader and more significant framework. We live in both exciting and challenging times. But I am optimistic. I believe society will develop a more intensive yet sustainable relationship with the ocean.

The programme runs until the end of August 2027. What are the prospects for an extension?

– That depends on whether we can demonstrate to Mistra that we are delivering results and will continue to do so in the future. But the outlook is promising.

Has C2B2’s relevance increased over time or declined?

– It has grown. The ocean is becoming an increasingly central topic. The challenges at sea largely revolve around how to balance competing interests. That is precisely what we are working on in this research programme.

Footnote: The interview with Torsten Linders was performed in February 2025.

Some numbers about C2B2 and the blue economy

C2B2's first annual report covers 2024, but it also represents the last four months of 2023, since the research programme was launched the first of September that year. The first 16 months have shown an exciting progress. Here are some figures about C2B2 and the Swedish blue economy.

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 Emanuela Vanacore, Frans Sjölander, Nikolaos Xafenias*,
 Siv Huseby (2024). Key economic figures of
 the blue economy in Sweden – Data brief.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15051814>
 * Corresponding author.

Data sources blue fields: *Swedish Transport Administration (2015), Vanacore et al. (2024) and the European Commission (2024).*

The new blue: Built-up seascapes create new maritime relations

Four representatives of the research programme, Mistra Co-Creating Better Blue, discuss maritime innovation in the context of a dawning new era for human presence and activities at sea.

We humans are builders. The most densely populated and most intensively exploited areas are built-up landscapes, where wood, stone, concrete and steel constructions dominate.

But the situation has been fundamentally different at sea for centuries and millennia. Here, human activities and presence have been almost exclusively associated with boats and ships, which, over time, have grown in size and capacity in line with our technological development.

These advances have enabled an increased human presence and activity at sea, which we often call the 'blue economy'. Although the broader definition of the 'blue economy' can include many sectors and stakeholders such as transport, fisheries, and military, these activities share a common factor: they rely exclusively on ships.

The role of offshore wind farms in the 'blue economy'

Today, in the early 2000s, we live in the dawn of a new era when the total dominance of ships is challenged by a new form of human presence and activity at sea: the rapid expansion of offshore wind farms.

The transformative effects of these developments are impossible to assess with certainty, but they must not be underestimated. We are referring to a vast number of massive permanent installations, each over 300 meters high, possibly spreading across the 70% of Earth's surface covered by the sea – areas where humans have never settled.

Currently, offshore wind farms are being built in relatively shallow areas of the continental shelf within national exclusive economic zones, up to 200 nautical miles from the coast. With the introduction of floating installations, the built-up seascape can theoretically be extended to any part of the sea.

Key precursors to the developed seascape can be found both on the seabed, with subsea cables dating back to the 1850s, and at sea level, with offshore oil and gas platforms

established since the 1950s. As important as these installations were at the time, they did not challenge the dominant role of ships in the blue economy, at least not in the way that offshore wind farms do today.

Offshore windfarms create a new built-up seascape

We argue firstly that offshore installations, such as wind farms, should be considered part of a built seascape, and secondly that the current expansion of the built-up seascape represents such a fundamental shift for the blue economy and the maritime sector that it is appropriate to speak of a 'new blue'.

We draw inspiration from another area, namely space, where we are experiencing a dramatic expansion of actors and the number and types of launched platforms in the 21st century. This is combined with diversified purposes for the platforms, including small, low-cost, low-orbit satellites for Earth observation and high-speed communications and crafts for private space tourism. This has been aptly called the 'new space'.

Relating to and navigating the 'new blue'

How should we relate to the 'new blue'? The most important thing is to accept the inherent uncertainties. Opportunities such as renewable energy, diverse use of infrastructure, and enhanced data acquisition, as well as challenges like competition for sea space, legal uncertainty, and potential environmental impacts, are becoming increasingly evident and are already subjects of intensive discussion and research. But it is unrealistic to say that we see all the relevant cascading effects, when we leave the old blue economy, exclusively based on temporary presence and ships, and enter the 'new blue' where permanent offshore installations are important and distinguishing features.

Navigating the 'new blue' is necessary for national policymakers to manage both positive opportunities and rapidly changing risks. For instance, during periods of heightened international tension, the data routinely collected by operators of offshore installations – both above and below the sea surface – can offer situational awareness that surpasses what dedicated military installations can provide.

Such awareness will facilitate both proper de-escalation

and appropriate response measures. If a military conflict breaks out, mastering naval warfare in the built-up seascape may be just as essential as urban warfare on land.

It is tempting to relate to innovation when thinking of the transformation in the "new blue". Let us do that. Innovation is commonly referred to as the new or redistributed value, outcomes, results, and impact adopted by the context, market, society, and citizens on planet Earth. We often unconsciously overlook the fact that for an innovation to be adopted by people and have an impact, we need to consciously use common language, metaphors, attractive guiding images, compelling wordings, and knowledge of relational processes.

These approaches address our human emotional and relational needs. Functional needs help us complete important tasks with the support of technology, however we often place greater emphasis on the technological and functional aspects of innovation and its processes, neglecting the relational and emotional ones.

Research on the new blue

The emotional and relational aspects of innovation are particularly relevant to consider in the 'new blue', as the built-up seascape challenges the established norm of human presence at sea, a norm that has been in place for centuries and millennia.

In the research programme Mistra Co-Creating Better Blue (C2B2), our approach to innovation is to engage old and new stakeholders of the Swedish blue economy in processes "from data to knowledge to decision and actions".

Essential to our concept are the three LivingLabs we launched in 2024. For more details about the C2B2 concept, see two previous presentations in Open Access Government (Wehn et al., 2023; Imperiale and Wehn, 2024).

The dramatic ocean data and knowledge increase

Emphasising data does not contradict the relational and emotional aspects of innovation. A significant element of the "new blue" is the dramatic increase in ocean data.

Most of our knowledge of the 70% of our planet covered by ocean is based on data gathered by ships and satellites. This increase in data also calls for advancing our knowledge of the ocean and "the new blue". The ocean is still almost a

data desert compared to the situation on land, especially compared to the built-up landscape.

This is now changing in all areas where the built-up seascape is spreading, with massive data acquisition both above and below the sea surface. Engaging stakeholders from different parts of society in co-creation around a comprehensive set of open and relevant data allows the creation of shared knowledge, images and stories. In these times of division and tension, C2B2 offers a positive vision of how we can govern a sustainable blue economy.

Footnote: [The article was first published in Open Access Government-magazine, January 2025.](#)

Jessica Hjerpe Olausson

Daniel Richardsson

Richard Hawkins

Torsten Linders

Blue economy sectors – Sweden

Data source: [Vancore et al. 2024](#)

Net investments over time (M€) – Sweden

Data source: [EU Blue Economy Observatory](#)

Robin Teigland: “C2B2’s role is to challenge”

The C2B board consists of a group of four people, experts in their respective fields, and is led by Robin Teigland, Professor of Strategy and Management of Digitalization at Chalmers.
 – A lot of exciting things are happening within C2B2, she says.

How does your role in the programme function?

– I lead the C2B2 board, which is responsible for strategic decisions and programme updates, publication of annual reports, and strategic initiatives that we consider important. We collaborate with the programme host, the University of Gothenburg, and the other parties in the programme.

How engaged are you?

– Very engaged, actually more than I had thought beforehand. I enjoy taking part, as it is not only a very interesting programme but also a wonderful opportunity to collaborate and learn in a complex inter-disciplinary organization with such skilled people.

Do you often have meetings with the representatives?

– I usually collaborate with the programme manager, sometimes every week. I have also had some contact with leaders for various work packages and LivingLabs.

What is your impression so far?

– There is a lot of excitement that has started within C2B2, and all the partners are very ambitious.

The LivingLabs working method – why is it effective?

– Well, if we are to truly succeed in achieving sustainable management of our ocean, then we must make sure that all parts of the blue economy pull in roughly the same direction. All activities and all stakeholders are needed in that work. With LivingLabs, the stakeholders collaborate together, on the issues that they together prioritize.

With so many different stakeholders – is it possible to achieve something concrete?

– That is the very challenge that C2B2 is supposed to crack. It is not easy, but you can also turn the question around. If each stakeholder works independently, how will we ever achieve sustainability? I don't think that's possible.

What role does a project like this play in society?

– It is only becoming more and more obvious how dependent our societies are on the ocean. It is about the climate, it is

about transport and energy and food, and well-being. We need to find ways to use the ocean without consuming it. Do you see any potential pitfalls that C2B2 would like to avoid?

– I hope that C2B2 will dare to challenge. The maritime world is sometimes a bit conservative and slow. If we only think within the old framework, then we might miss out on fantastic opportunities.

The blue economy is developing rapidly – what possible developments do you see?

– Hmm. I don't think it's my role to point out any scenario for the programme. At least not yet, at this point, but maybe later in connection with the board making a decision on a strategic investment. But I think it's very good that C2B2 has not just one LivingLab, but three. They have the opportunity to follow partly different tracks, and in this way explore different paths.

Something about yourself – what else do you work on?

– In addition to being a professor of Management of Digitalization at Chalmers University of Technology, I am also a blue economy entrepreneur. Under the Peniche Ocean Watch Initiative, we are building a circular economy ecosystem across Portugal and Sweden that upcycles fishing nets into new products for local markets using large-scale additive manufacturing.

Your own background is in economics, how important is that perspective regarding a sustainable blue economy?

– To truly succeed in co-creating a better blue future, we need to develop a methodology for how to best involve and ensure value creation for all stakeholders. This is a challenging task especially when leveraging disruptive technologies. I am convinced that an interorganizational management perspective is a crucial driving factor to achieving real change.

Robin Teigland

The Navy chief went ashore – and left C2B2's board

For a year and a half, she was part of C2B2's board.

But at the end of October 2024, it became clear that Navy Commander Ewa Skoog Haslum was appointed as the new head of the Armed Forces' operations management. In connection with the change, she also ended her involvement within C2B2.

– There is tremendous competence in the programme, which I am now unfortunately leaving, she says.

In her job as a naval commander, her professional residence has been out on Muskö. Classic ground in Swedish naval, military contexts. But when the newsletter gets hold of Ewa Skoog Haslum, she is in a place that is more associated with her new job.

– I am sitting at the headquarters on Lidingövägen, she says.

An interview with an officer at her level is associated with certain security procedures. The telephone call is administered via a press officer who is also present, albeit inaudible, during the call. If they completed a background check before the interview? Of course.

– He fixes all that, says Ewa Skoog Haslum.

She refers to the press officer. But contact with C2B2 began in a more informal way. C2B2's programme manager simply got in touch via LinkedIn.

– He asked if I wanted to join the board, says Ewa Skoog Haslum.

What really got her interested was the view of the ocean featured in the programme.

– In various contexts there is talk of a rural area. But I usually say that there is also a society out at sea. A sea village. A flow of communication, energy, travellers, economy ... even crime, she says.

All parts of society should be involved

Within C2B2 there is a perspective around creating a sustainable management of the sea where different stakeholders in the maritime community cooperate. Because if we are to build a sustainable seaside village – then, according to Ewa Skoog Haslum, all parts of society need to be involved. One type of stakeholder participating in the research programme is companies in offshore wind power. There, the navy may have views on the location, so that it does not compromise their manoeuvring space. In her role as head of the navy,

Ewa Skoog Haslum has also said that there are business risks in locating the wind farms outside Swedish territorial waters, i.e. further than twelve nautical miles from the coast.

– I am not saying that it

is always inappropriate. But you should be aware that the Swedish defence has no legal right to protect them out there. This makes you vulnerable, and you may also have to be prepared for an antagonist to simply take over the investment.

A result of us bowing down to a greater power? No, she doesn't think so.

– It's about us being robust.

When asked what she thinks about the possibility for the work in C2B2 to be successful, she points to a particular strength: the cooperation between the various stakeholders and partners who participate.

– If you want to be successful when it comes to things like blue economy and security, you don't just need knowledge. It also requires to be brave and a little noisy in the debate. Durability noisy. And each doesn't say it as forcefully on its own. Together is the key word, she says.

An exemplary way of working

She believes that the combined skills found within C2B2 is an exemplary way of working.

– More people should adopt that. It is when we cluster different competencies that we become strong.

“It requires to be brave and a little noisy in the debate”

As a naval commander, she has a professional relationship with the sea that has lasted a long time.

– It's the element I've been in since I was 19.

Then, in 1987, she did her military service in the navy. But even in private, the relationship is solid. Ewa Skoog Haslum grew up in Torekov on the Bjäre Peninsula. A classic fishing village that over the years has become more and more of an epicentre for typical vacationers: celebrities and others who want to live near the sea without necessarily having it as their

livelihood. She herself lives today in Stockholm. But there, too, the sea is close, and the former navy commander likes to venture out into the archipelago even in his spare time.

– Sailboat? No, for us it's the engine that counts, she says.

Ewa Skoog Haslum

Age: 56 years.

Family: Husband and two sons.

Lives: Stockholm.

Listening to: “A strong musical memory is from when I was ship commander of the corvette Sundsvall and we came home from a long-term UN mission. When we docked in Stockholm, we played U2's It's a Beautiful Day. It felt powerful.”

Moving on. Smart management of our sea basins is an important issue for a Navy chief, and former Navy chief Ewa Skoog Haslum was involved in C2B2's board before she changed jobs to chief of the Defence Staff in mid-November. She thinks that several different stakeholders are brought together and try to find out something together – as in C2B2 – is a good way of working.

– It is when we cluster different competencies that we become strong, she says.

Co-creating a sustainable blue economy for Sweden

Wehn, Linders and Barquet explain how the MISTRA C2B2 programme is working to bring about transformative change in participatory ocean governance in Sweden

The ocean – the new frontier of human activity – is being redefined by new discoveries, technologies, national strategies, and ecological imperatives. Yet, it is undeniable that the status of most seas is in decay – and if the goal would be to restore or improve their status, then most human activities should be banned.

Instead, we witness that, in recent years, the blue economy is promoted as an answer to energy and food insecurity, as well as to an increased demand for shipping of goods, and

transport of people and services. So, humanity depends on marine livelihoods, but the blue economy is also rapidly increasing pressure on the long-term sustainability of marine ecosystems.

From a blue growth-based approach towards a sustainable blue economy

There is an urgent need to radically change the way we think and use the ocean, away from a blue growth-based approach and towards a sustainable blue economy.

Marine industries are changing at high speed while technology is evolving fast. Ocean governance is, however, lagging behind due to little physical presence in the ocean; sparse, patchy and expensive data collection; and conflicting goals among stakeholders over the use of the marine space.

Interests clash from opposing goals; on the one hand, to protect our ocean and achieve the climate goals, and on the other hand, to expand the blue economy to tackle socio-economic challenges such as transport, food, and energy security.

Additionally, openness and inclusiveness in ocean governance also lag dramatically behind due to low levels of ocean literacy, poor awareness of ocean-related challenges, and data coverage several orders of magnitudes worse than on land and in the coastal zone.

Transformative change in ocean governance in Sweden

Moving away from blue growth and towards a sustainable blue economy requires a transformation in the way we think

about the marine space and the activities increasingly deployed in our seas. As a larger part of society has an ever-increasing stake in the ocean, it is imperative that we develop new forms of stakeholder collaboration combined with science-based ecosystem governance practices.

This is particularly urgent in Sweden where our relationship with and dependency on the ocean have changed dramatically during living memory, from being one of Europe's major shipbuilding and fishing countries, to using the ocean mainly as a route for export/import, and the coast for leisure.

Now, we need to re-engage with our extensive and very diverse offshore areas in new ways, via marine renewable energy production, by implementing knowledge-based marine spatial planning, and by sustainably managing the ecosystem services of our ocean. Sweden needs a sound yet flexible

approach to deal with the biogeographical, and social-economic diversity related to the governance of a sustainable blue economy from the northernmost part of Gulf of Bothnia all the way to Skagerrak.

Co-creating Better Blue

The Mistra C2B2 programme – Co-creating Better Blue – focuses on addressing what we deem as the real challenge of the coming decade: governing multiple demands in increasingly claimed and fragile marine ecosystems.

C2B2 envisions a more sustainable, open and democratic, multi-sector and multi-actor blue economy and sustainable society. We aim to trigger transformative change in ocean governance in Sweden away from a single-use/single-actor paradigm, and towards multifunctional use through co-creation founded on data for ecosystem resilience.

Giving nature a voice

Key to this transformation is reimagining the role of quintuple helix actors (academia, industry, government, civil society, and the natural environment) across the blue economy in

processes ‘from data to knowledge to decisions and action’ (see Figure 1), increasing opportunities for participation, deliberation and influence, building open infrastructure, and strengthening capacity to support the inclusion of data and knowledge in multilevel governance. In this transformation, data is elevated as the means to ‘give nature a voice.’

Aims and pathways

Mistra C2B2 is creating the conditions for a robust, inclusive, and just transition towards participatory ocean governance by pursuing three interrelated aims:

- To provide the basis for a continuously evolving knowledge system for science-based ecosystem governance in Sweden by advancing and interlinking three pillars: ecosystems and climate science; open, data-driven innovation and emerging technology; and governance theory and practice;
- To demonstrate in practice in three LivingLabs related to Sweden’s marine basins, how the transition towards science-based ecosystem governance of a sustainable blue economy can be achieved by initiating, developing and embedding co-creation processes as routines for participatory

governance, ensuring adaptive management practices beyond the C2B2 programme lifetime (see Figure 2); and

- To reshape our relationship with the ocean by instilling new ways of working together and practicing science-based ecosystem governance, so that more actors and individuals can realise that they (could) have a direct stake in the offshore space.

Distinct pathways will ensure successful achievement of our ambitions, including:

- Data: Change how data about the ocean is produced, perceived, and accepted, accessed, combined, and used in science, policy and society;
- People: Enhance who is engaged in ocean governance and how they participate and embed these new participation practices; and
- Systems: Strengthen the interactions of stakeholders locally and across multi-level governance; and strengthen existing approaches such as marine spatial planning to be more integrative and sector sensitive.

The Mistra C2B2 approach provides the basis for paving the way for transitions towards governing multiple demands

in increasingly claimed and fragile marine ecosystems. The extensive demonstration and validation of the Mistra C2B2 approach, with 12 partners from academia and research organisations, and initially 25 co-funding associated partners from industry and public sector, as well as stakeholders from civil society, means it can also be replicated elsewhere in Sweden and internationally.

Footnote: [The article was first published in Open Access Government-magazine, October 2023. Last modified 30th October 2023.](#)

Uta Wehn

Torsten Linders

Karina Barquet

Sustainability transformations in marine governance in Sweden via social learning

Dr. Angelo Jonas Imperiale and Dr. Uta Wehn describe the MISTRA C2B2 programme's unique approach to promoting sustainability transformations in Sweden's marine governance through social learning in LivingLabs.

The MISTRA programme Co-creating Better Blue (C2B2) aims to transform current marine governance in Sweden towards a more participatory and data-driven approach.

This approach seeks to enhance the resilience of marine social-ecological systems and achieve a sustainable blue economy in Sweden.

A tailored methodology for the co-creation of LivingLabs informs the overall C2B2 programme and is vital to achieving its desired outcomes. This methodology guides the develop-

ment of three LivingLabs involving relevant blue economy sectors and actors in three marine basins in Sweden. It is based on an innovative participatory approach focussed on fostering transformative learning among the multiple C2B2 LivingLabs' stakeholders, the organisations to which they belong, and the governance setting in which they operate.

Social learning is key

Social learning broadly refers to any change in understanding that takes place in the individuals involved and their wider social units, organisations or communities of practice within society.

Social learning outcomes differ in scale and depth, spanning from individual to organisational and institutional settings and from single-loop (i.e. acquisition of new knowledge and skills) to multiple-loop learning (i.e. transformative learning)

and outcomes, fostering changes in attitudes, behaviours, routines, strategies, procedures, policies and norms.

In environmental governance, social learning is a crucial process for fostering transformative change in environmental governance regimes, aiming to enhance the resilience and sustainability of social-ecological systems and the sustainable management of natural resources within such systems. Broadly, the literature discusses the enabling conditions for social learning processes to occur in environmental governance regimes.

Three basic, nested and inter-level dynamics enable social learning, thus leading to adaptive environmental governance and resilience-building across multiple governance levels and social-ecological scales:

- Horizontal interactions enable social learning to occur among stakeholders, a broader constituency of (local)

communities, sectors and decision-makers at the same governance level.

- Upward integrations of knowledge & learnings enable interactions and social learning among actors at multiple governance levels and facilitate the integration and scaling up of lower-level social learning outcomes and sustainability transformations across broader social-ecological scales.
- Downward regulations enable recursive social learning among actors across multiple governance levels, strengthening both horizontal interactions and upward integrations in a continuous process of collaborative problem-solving and sustainability transformation. This ultimately leads to multi-level adaptive environmental governance and co-management approaches.

To make these three social learning dynamics happen and

Photo: Pixabay, Pexels

Transformation ahead. An enhanced resilience of marine social-ecological systems is in focus for the MISTRA programme Co-creating Better Blue.

create participatory and adaptive environmental governance and management regimes, there are four cross-cutting issues to consider:

- Content (i.e., learning what and why?).
- Process (i.e., learning how?).
- Internal context (i.e., learning by whom and in which organisational setting?); and
- External context (i.e., learning in face of which external challenges and opportunities?).
- Sustainability transformation: Stakeholder participation is not enough

Sustainability transformation: Stakeholder participation is not enough

The scope and desired outcomes of enhancing social learning have often been associated with processes that foster public participation. However, it cannot be assumed that participatory processes inevitably lead to social learning. Indeed, social learning has often been confused with the conditions and methods that enable it to occur, with many projects claiming to be social learning projects.

Yet many rarely go beyond simply facilitating stakeholder participation, providing little or no evidence of the social learning taking place. These shortcomings are common to most research and practices concerned with public involvement, including traditional LivingLabs methods and approaches. While LivingLabs have been widely recognised as a valuable tool that can enable meaningful multi-level stakeholder engagement, there is still a lack of research concerning the enabling dynamics and dimensions of social learning that LivingLabs could enhance and the different social learning outcomes that can be achieved in the context of LivingLabs fostering sustainable environmental governance and management.

Enabling factors in place

In the Mistra C2B2 programme, the tailored LivingLabs methodology addresses these gaps and guides the design and implementation of the LivingLabs to ensure that:

- The content, process and context-related factors that enable social learning are in place; and
- The C2B2 LivingLabs can effectively contribute to achieving the transformative learning outcomes and changes needed to achieve a more sustainable blue economy and resilient social-ecological marine system in Sweden.
- Content: Co-develop a shared vision among the LivingLabs stakeholders of the common problems and needs that should be addressed, as well as the desired

outcomes to be achieved. • A co-designed social learning agenda will make this shared vision operational in terms of:

- The specific LivingLabs activities to be implemented to realise this vision and
- The specific transformative learning outcomes that need to be reached at the individual, organisational and governance levels to accomplish such a vision fully.
- Process: Ground all LivingLabs activities in transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes and negotiation, and fully embed inclusiveness as a key leading principle informing the design and implementation of all C2B2 LivingLabs-related activities.
- Context: Ensure that the LivingLabs carefully reflect local needs and desires to create tangible local value for all stakeholders, concrete incentives for overcoming typical motivational barriers, and structure and support to foster active participation.

In sum, the C2B2 LivingLabs methodology combines the strengths of LivingLabs as recently applied to sustainable environmental governance and urban and spatial planning, with a deeper understanding of operational aspects of social learning. By focussing on enhancing transformative learning within and across the three C2B2 LivingLabs, the Mistra C2B2 programme will drive sustainability transformations in ocean governance and management, thus contributing to achieving a more participatory and adaptive marine spatial planning and sustainable blue economy in Sweden.

Footnote: [The article was first published in Open Access Government-magazine, October 2024.](#)

Uta Wehn

Angelo Jonas Imperiale

A slightly different research

Ready to go. Jessica Hjerpe Olausson who leads the LivingLabs West. At the moment she has just revealed the focus for the work package: Southern Skagerrak.

Cooperation. When LivingLabs West had their first meeting the participants soon got into discussions about the governance of Southern Skagerrak.

Great interest when two LivingLabs started

Central to C2B2 are the so-called LivingLabs, which will take place in three locations in Sweden – in the west, east and north. During September, two of them were launched, LivingLab East and LivingLab West.

The idea within LivingLabs is to create a forum where a number of marine actors can meet, everything from fisheries and wind power companies to researchers and authorities and more. Together, they must discuss, experiment, identify knowledge gaps and resolve conflicts.

– A kind of workshops where we work together, says Karina Barquet, research leader focusing on coasts and oceans at the Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI) and linked to C2B2 as leader of LivingLab East.

Eager to know more

Together with the members of C2B2's team, there were good discussions, among other things the stakeholders wanted to know more about what the programme can achieve.

– Our stakeholders were curious and wanted more information, says Karina Barquet,

According to her, however, at this early stage of a LivingLab, the questions usually outnumber the answers.

– This is a slightly different research project; it is not like most others. Here it is about us identifying challenges together, finding solutions, and working collectively to make a difference. Sometimes it is called action research. What results will we achieve? We don't really know that yet. We will discover that together, she says.

According to Karina Barquet, the results will be important in different ways.

– Not least because this part of Sweden has found itself in a new situation due to the geopolitical situation with what is happening on the other side of the Baltic Sea.

On September 24, also LivingLab West had its kick-off meeting. It took place at the RISE/SSPA Maritime Center in Gothenburg. About 20 people participated.

– It was the first time we met our stakeholders, says Jessica Hjerpe Olausson, senior project manager at RISE (Research Institutes of Sweden) and leader of LivingLab West.

Among the stakeholders are representatives from several different industries: the fishing industry, the shipping sector, offshore wind power, companies that work with data management and more. Authorities at municipal and regional level also participated.

According to Jessica Hjerpe Olausson, the idea is to discuss together, and eventually come up with joint proposals, around initiatives that improve Swedish marine management.

– In order for the ideas to be as good as possible, we have invited widely, she says.

On September 10, several actors met for an online start-up meeting for LivingLab East. Later this fall, they plan to meet physically in Stockholm, and in the spring in Blekinge. After that, Gotland is proposed as a meeting place. The digital start-up meeting was successful according to Karina Barquet.

– Yes, it felt good. We were close to twenty people from different places in Sweden who met, she says.

Focus on Southern Skagerrak

During the gathering, participants received an introduction to the programme, plus they received information about the geographic area LivingLab West targets: southern Skagerrak.

An area where, among other things, there are applications to build offshore wind power in three locations.

– At the meeting we discussed, among other things, what different interests the stakeholders have in the area we focus on, and what challenges they see ahead, says Jessica Hjerpe Olausson.

The next meeting will be later this fall. Also, next spring, there will be a meeting for LivingLab West – online or physically.

When do will you be up and running at full pace?

– The dialogue already feels fruitful. There were constructive dialogues immediately and everyone listened to each other.

What do you hope you will achieve in the long run?

– How to work with participatory processes around ocean management, and that Sweden takes a step forward in this. We are not used to working inclusively in that way in this country. Hopefully our work will contribute to a growing blue economy while we have healthy seas.

Three participants at the kick-off meeting: What do you expect from LivingLab West?

Kristina Fermiskog, environmental investigator, the city of Gothenburg.

– It is a very good approach, and a neutral platform, which makes it possible to get help with what we see needs to be done. That is, to cooperate to strengthen the blue economy and make it a significant part of the food system, sustainable supply of food and energy plus creating jobs.

Lennart Bjärknemyr, tour boat skipper, Daisy Sea Fishing.

– A strong focus on the state of the sea. You see land-dwelling creatures, but not the sea-dwelling ones, and there are very few who focus on what happens below the surface. I hope that the decision-making authorities will get a better overall approach via this project.

Stefan Gustavsson, responsible for public relations, Eolus wind.

– I hope that it can increase the understanding of physically coexisting on the same sea surface. We depend on being able to build wind power where the electricity is needed, where the situation with wind and bottom conditions are good. Plus, where it's close to a connection.

“The economy is crucial to achieve a change”

Researchers, stakeholders and partners ... many are involved in how things are going in C2B2.

But even outside the group of active people there are others who follow the research programme closely. Like Mattias Rust at the Government Office.

– That type of horizontal research is very exciting, he says.

Mattias Rust describes himself as a non-political civil servant, attached to the Ministry of Rural Affairs and Infrastructure under Minister Andreas Carlson. The formal title is Chancellor's Council.

– A kind of layer between the expert authorities and politics, which, among other things, provides the political leadership with special knowledge and carries out many of their initiatives, such as EU negotiations and more, he says.

However, he is not just any civil servant who has been randomly assigned to a subject area. Mattias Rust has academic knowledge in what he works with.

– Yes, I'm a marine biologist at heart and worked for a while with research, he says.

Before he started at the government office, he, among other things, worked for a while in an EU-funded project on transboundary marine protected areas along the east coast of Africa.

A new strategy is underway

Today, he is involved in the work with the government's new maritime strategy, with a deeper focus on Sweden's seas and its industries.

According to Mattias Rust, integrated ocean management is something that made its way from research environments and further into the world of policy in the early 2000s. He mentions, for example, the more than ten-year-old Marine Planning Directive as ground-breaking.

– They began to look at the sea in a new way, as a whole in the administration.

The concept of sustainable blue economy which is established

today – has passed other expressions along the way.

– Blue growth for example. In that process, of concretizing the concepts and taking them from thought to action, research has been important.

At work, Mattias Rust continuously keeps track of what is happening in academia when it comes to things in his field of work, and one of the research programmes he follows is C2B2.

Important with financial incentives

He believes that, as in C2B2, to broadly involving the industries that have interests in the marine environment is an important success factor.

– The financial issue is crucial to gaining momentum in a change. The biggest innovations tend to come where there is money to be made. I am convinced that financial incentives are important, not least for the blue economy.

He says that one of the challenges for research projects that want to achieve decisive changes in the blue economy as a whole is not to get stuck in too narrow a niche.

– I think it's exciting to meet people who actually take in the broader perspective, and I think C2B2 hits the nail on the head there.

Will you continue to follow the work within C2B2 in the future?

– Absolutely. I assume that the contact between us will be continuous.

Do you miss working with research yourself?

– Not in the sense that I would like to be a researcher. I have probably moved in the more comprehensive policy world for too long. But if I ever change jobs, I could very well imagine working closer to the world of research, with different policy ideas around, for example, the blue economy. Applied research plays an extremely important role in the transition.

Is there something exciting happening around marine issues in your world right now?

– One example is that after the summer, Ursula von der Leyen sent out a so-called mission letter about an Ocean Pact to incoming commissioners. No one knows yet exactly what that pact will be about. But for those of us who work with the broad blue issues, it is exciting that the EU's highest leader comes with such a signal.

Follows C2B2. – I like that type of research programme, with a broad angle of attack, says Mattias Rust, chancellor at the Government Office.

Reviews with software.
Samuel Morsbach, PhD student at C2B2 examines marine environments using the program Ecopath with Ecosim.

Software gives answers about the sea

Reviews with software. Samuel Morsbach, PhD student at C2B2 examines marine environments using the program Ecopath with Ecosim.

He has his workplace at the Tjärnö Marina laboratory. There, Samuel Morsbach sits by his computer, immersed in analyses of how things like offshore wind power and other things affect the marine environment.

– It is a very special tool I work with, he says.

The software Ecopath with Ecosim* is developed by several researchers with a focus on marine environments. A program that is notoriously complicated to use, with at least a year's break-in period – for an expert – before results can be obtained.

But Samuel Morsbach, PhD student at the Department of Marine Sciences at the University of Gothenburg, thinks the picture is a bit exaggerated.

– If you're investigating human impact on marine ecosystems, then it is really good to have. But I wouldn't call it rocket science, he says.

Samuel Morsbach is attached to Mistra C2B2's work package 1, Open ecosystems and climate change. He is also involved in work package 4, Living labs.

His mother tongue is German, he comes from Hamburg, but after less than a year as a doctoral student, he speaks fluent Swedish.

– Although, there is an explanation for that. My parents have a cottage between Örnsköldsvik and Sundsvall, and I was also an exchange student in Flen when I went to high school.

Plugs in data and makes simulations

In his doctoral thesis, he uses Ecopath with Ecosim to analyse how, for example, an offshore wind turbine affects the animal life in the surrounding sea. The program does simulations based on the data he puts in, then he draws conclusions.

– For example, it could be about porpoises and how they react to changes in the environment, and to the underwater noise that the power plant creates. According to Samuel Morsbach, the big challenge of working

in Ecopath with Ecosim, is entering relevant data into the model.

– There is a lot of data to be found that deals with the entire North Sea, but I have to be able to break it down to the specific area that I am investigating, he says.

Even without having access to advanced software – or even being a researcher at all – it is still possible to draw some correct conclusions about how the bottom environment is affected by a construction such as a wind turbine. Like that it is an obvious advantage for the fish stock that it is not possible to trawl in an offshore wind farm, which at least at first glance may seem positive.

– But I would be careful to say that. The fish, they lose areas of their natural bottom environment, which they obviously perceive as bad.

Samuel Morsbach himself does not take a position on what is good or bad. As a researcher, he has no bias, the results must be able to stand for themselves without a filter of personal opinions.

– The job is about analysing the effects and finding the best solution, he says.

Digital models

So far, he has no results to present. He says that the first months of work were spent mostly on planning and getting an idea of what is possible.

– After that, I spent the summer building digital models. But it takes a long time to find the right format, and to feed the model with the right information. Now I look forward to receiving feedback on my models from various stakeholders.

Even though working with the software has its challenges, he thinks the job is fun.

– It's like a private eye investigation where you have to find information that doesn't exist yet. Anyone who sees me sitting in front of the computer all day might think it looks boring, but to me it's a bit like working on a complicated puzzle.

** Footnote: The first versions of Ecopath came already in 1984. The software has been developed over the years and a simulation function has been added.*

A Glider takes shape

It may seem a bit inconspicuous to a passerby, just an anonymous metal door on a street in the former shipyard area at Lindholmen in Gothenburg. But inside – at the research laboratory Revere, a part of Chalmers University of Technology – cutting-edge activities regarding vehicle research are carried out, which, among other things, also have bearing on C2B2.

Inside the door opens an airy warehouse, with several meters in ceiling height, and which swallows several bulky objects. A truck, a passenger car, a chassis for a smaller home-built racing car. A large aluminium boat.

The vehicles are included in various research projects, among other things with a focus on technology for autonomous vehicles and craft. On this particular day, the lab is responsible for a large stand at the Swedish Exhibition and Congress Centre – a fairground in Gothenburg, so the room is quite empty of people. Ola Benderius, associate professor, and Tarun Kadri Sathiyam, doctoral student – both at the De-

***The Glider.** Ola Benderius, associate professor, and Tarun Kadri Sathiyam, doctoral student, build a glider. Among the components that make up the device is a long carbon fiber tube.*

partment of Mechanics and Maritime Sciences at Chalmers – have the room to themselves. They lift out an impact-resistant black plastic case, about one and a half meters long. From it they unpack a long carbon fiber tube with a diameter of around a couple of decimetres. With the help of a 3D printer, they have produced a pointed yellow top for the tube, plus a cap that plugs the back end.

The construction is called "a glider". A kind of measuring instrument that slowly moves through water.

Measures ten times per second

The glider they are working with is part of C2B2's work package 2: Open, data-driven innovation and new technologies.

It has sensors connected to equipment on the inside. During movements in the water, the sensors record depth, water temperature and salinity. On the journey through different water layers, it measures the various parameters ten times per second.

As for how it can move forward in the water, the glider is equipped with an ingenious construction. With the help of a pressurized oil-filled bladder – a so-called buoyancy engine – the glider can change its own buoyancy and thus rise or fall.

It can also adjust its angle of attack by moving its own battery forward and backward.

The batteries are moved to tilt the glider pointing down or up by 20 degrees. And when falling or rising this angle – and with a little help from small wings attached to the tube – it will result in a force forward.

Thanks to this clever "hack" of the laws of physics, the craft moves forward, using almost no energy at all. The distance to the bottom becomes the decisive factor for how far the craft travels when it dives.

– Depending on how deep it is at the current location, the glider chooses a certain maximum depth, for example 70 meters, says Ola Benderius.

The dive takes place in a long slow motion, which for this particular glider will last about an hour.

Eventually, when it comes to the surface, the computers in the laboratory on land can locate it and automatically set a new course with a new maximum depth, and let the glider set off again.

– Once it is released into the sea, it is supposed to be able to stay out and dive for months, says Ola Benderius.

In addition to distinct research-related purposes, there are also other contexts where the elongated construction could be useful.

– For example, for companies that work with offshore wind power, they want to have various facts about the area before they start building, says Tarun Kadri Sathiyam.

To optimize the glider's ability before it is released into the water, they have used a so-called hardware in the loop simulation.

– We have connected the glider's sensors directly to a computer, says Ola Benderius.

They have then provided the sensors with synthetic data, giving the researchers the opportunity to evaluate and optimize the function while the device is still on a workbench.

As for the outer construction itself, it is almost fascinatingly simple, made with materials that are relatively easy to buy or make yourself. Despite the simplicity, it takes some working hours to get the slider ready.

Students helped out

In addition to Ola Benderius and Tarun Kadri Sathiyam, around twenty students at Chalmers University of Technology have invested time in the project.

A lot of value in the form of working time is thus invested in the process. Even the measuring equipment itself is expensive, and since the glider cannot steer away if it encounters an obstacle in the way, there is some danger of it colliding with something and potentially being lost.

They must always keep that risk in mind.

– But of course we will avoid releasing it into waterways or the like, says Tarun Kadri Sathiyam.

“Some saw their research go up in smoke”

Life as a natural science researcher often involves collecting data. There are several good reasons to store that information in open archives for research data, according to David Rayner at the Swedish National Data Service (SND).

– Not least because your research data can disappear. If you have shared them via an open archive, that risk is reduced, he says.

Shared data also provides opportunities to improve one's work.

– You open up to, for example, the possibility of receiving important opinions before your article is published. If you are

transparent, the credibility of your research is strengthened, says David Rayner, who is connected to C2B2 as an expert on data storage.

Potential for attention

Anyone who shares their data publicly also creates potential for other researchers to pay attention to the work and build on it.

– It creates ripples on the water. When your data is cited, others will discover your research.

Many times, research journals and financiers also require that research data be reported in a transparent manner.

Another strong reason to share is that information stored in an open archive leads a significantly safer life. According to David Rayner, it is not entirely unusual for researchers to store their data on platforms that have been shut down or

changed in such a way that the material has disappeared.

– People have seen research data go up in smoke for good because they didn't use platforms dedicated to long-term storage, he says.

According to David Rayner, it is a common misconception that data in an open archive must be freely downloadable.

– But that's not the case, it can be limited in different ways.

Secure storage

C2B2 supports the so-called FAIR model. It requires data to be stored securely with sustainable availability, regardless of whether it is shared freely or if researchers must apply for access.

– We are convinced of the importance of marine research data being shared widely, everyone wins, says David Rayner.

And for those who have not yet found a method to archive

their material in an effective and safe way, he and his colleagues at SND offer to contribute with concrete advice.

– Just get in touch. Taking care of data in a safe way is something of a mission for us, we are happy to help, he says.

Read more:

[C2B2 supports publishing marine data!](#)

[The FAIR principle](#)

David Rayner

